

THE CONCEPT OF SALES CONTRACT AND ITS TYPES

Quthmuratov Farxad Qalbaevich - PhD in Law, Associate Professor

Abdibaeva Jamila Aqpolat qizi - student of the Faculty of Law of Karakalpak State University

Abstract: This article provides an opinion on the concept of a sales contract, its essence, the procedure for concluding a sales contract, its regulation, signs of a sales contract.

Key words: sales contract, signs, types, seller, buyer, goods

Sales relations are one of the contracts that have been used by mankind since ancient times. With the settlement of commodity-money relations in the society, various tradesmen had the opportunity to buy and consume the products of other tradesmen's labor and at the same time to sell the products of their own labor.

According to the sales contract, one party (the seller) undertakes to transfer the goods to the other party (the buyer) as property, and the buyer undertakes to accept the goods and pay the specified amount of money (price) for this (Citizenship of the Republic of Uzbekistan Article 386, Part 1 of the Code)

By its legal nature, the sales contract is part of the set of obligations to transfer property rights or property rights from one person to another. At the same time, there are legal features that distinguish this contract from other similar contracts, which include: First of all, the sales contract is a (paid) contract. In this case, the buyer always pays a certain amount of money (soums, currency) in exchange for the property (goods) handed over by the seller;

Secondly, the sales contract belongs to the group of consensual contracts. In other words, the rights and obligations between the parties under this contract come into being from the moment all important terms of the contract are mutually agreed upon and the contract is formalized in the appropriate form:

Thirdly, according to the composition of contractual relations, it is a bilateral contract. As can be seen from the above definition of the consolidated contract, two

parties - the seller and the buyer - participate in this contract, and both parties have certain rights and obligations, the seller is obliged to deliver the item and receive a fee for it. will have the right. and the recipient has the obligation to pay the value of the item (goods) and the right to demand that the sold item be handed over to him.

The rules on the form of transactions (Civil Code, Articles 108-112), as well as the rules on the form of the contract (Civil Code, Article 336) apply to the form of the sales contract. In this case, the type of contract and the characteristics of the goods are important. In determining the form of the sales contract, firstly, the requirements of civil transactions, and secondly, the need to control the legality of sales transactions, the need to ensure the protection of the interests of society or the interests of certain individuals in such relations are the determining factors. For example, in the case of cash-based retail sales, for the convenience of the parties, special formalization of the sales contract is not required. A sale and purchase contract concluded for cash and executed at the time of its formation. as a general rule, regardless of the amount, it can be made in oral form. Therefore, sales contracts concluded in trade stores and markets are verbal because the goods are handed over to the buyers immediately and the fee is paid immediately.

The parties in the sales contract are the seller and the buyer. Citizens and legal entities can participate as parties. At the same time, in certain cases, the state can also participate as a party to the contract.

Both parties participating in the sales contract are responsible for non-fulfillment of their obligations under the law or contract.

The seller is responsible to the buyer in the following cases.

- a) fails to deliver the sold goods or delays delivery;
- b) does not warn the buyer about the existence of rights of third parties in the sold goods;
- d) conditions regarding the quantity and assortment of goods sold violates or sells poor quality goods.

The buyer, in turn, is responsible to the seller in the following cases:

- a) does not pay the fee for the sold goods or delays the payment.
- b) fails to accept the sold goods on time or delays the acceptance.

Article 390 of the Civil Code defines the moment of the seller's obligation to deliver the goods. Based on this, unless otherwise stipulated in the contract of sale, the seller's duty to hand over the goods to the buyer is considered fulfilled at the following times:

if the contract provides for the obligation to deliver the goods, during the delivery of the goods to the buyer or the person designated by him;

if the goods must be delivered to the buyer at the place where the goods are, at the time of handing over the goods to the buyer; The goods are considered to have been handed over to the buyer when the goods are ready to be handed over to the buyer at the appropriate place within the period stipulated in the contract, and when the buyer is informed that the goods are ready to be handed over in accordance with the terms of the contract. If the conformity of the goods for the purposes of the contract has not been confirmed by marking or in some other way, the goods are not considered ready for delivery.

If the defects of the goods were not reported by the seller, the seller, who delivered the goods of poor quality, at the request of the buyer:

exchange for a product of the same brand (model, article) of the same quality;

replacing the purchase price with a product of another brand (model, article) of the same quality;

eliminate the defects of the goods free of charge or cover the costs incurred by the buyer or a third party to eliminate the defects of the goods;

proportionately reduce the purchase price;

should compensate for the damage (Article 434 of the Civil Code).

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